

Heckman, RFM, and Ensemble Methods for Optimizing Marketing Campaign Performance

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Abstract

A major challenge in email marketing for a fundraising organization is to build a participant selection model that can help achieve higher response rates for all the events. New models to more accurately explain and predict response, as well as models that will allow accurate scoring of participants for higher donation, would be useful for organizations where return on investment is less than desired. We offer event-level participant and donor models that help target the right participants and donors to ensure a higher participation rate for all the events. The project uses statistical methodologies and techniques to derive insights from the data to build relationships between past and future participants. The project yields results that are significant in showing that by targeting the suggested set of participants, event participation can be increased and campaign costs decreased.

Keywords: Classification model, Logistic regression, Email marketing

1 Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is the third leading cause [1] of death in America, claiming the lives of 142,943 Americans annually. The disease is estimated to affect 24

million people, including 800,000 in Illinois. Asthma, a disease similar to COPD, affects 23 million people [2] in the United States, including 750,000 in Illinois.

The Client of our industry partner, **The Client Organization (a U.S.-based non-profit focused on public health initiatives)**, addresses not only COPD and asthma, but also lung cancer, tobacco control, and air quality through a comprehensive approach involving research, education, and advocacy activities. It serves people living with lung disease through community-based interventions, including helping with research grants, creating policy initiatives that address long-term concerns about respiratory diseases, and developing programs to prevent lung disease.

The Client Organization educates people about asthma management strategies, offers flu vaccinations, and provides smoking cessation counseling. Their wide range of community partnerships is fundamental to the success of their educational initiatives. To complement community-based research and programming efforts, **The Client Organization** advocates for lung-friendly policies throughout Chicago, Illinois, and the United States. With the help of community volunteers, the organization has been influential in passing legislation for smoke-free environments, limiting air pollution generated by power plants and diesel vehicles, and protecting the rights of children to carry life-saving asthma inhalers at school.

1.1 Problem Statement

The Client Organization (a U.S.-based non-profit focused on public health initiatives) relies primarily on donations for its funding. Its work is supported by the generous contributions and sponsorships of individuals, businesses, and foundations across Chicago. The organization conducts several athletic and social fundraising events, including its marquee event, “*EventB*,” a race up 94 floors of the Tower in Chicago. Participants register for these events by paying a small fee (approximately \$50) and then reach out to their networks to raise donations for **The Client Organization**. These supporters are referred to as donors.

Despite steady participation, most events are not filled to capacity and often fall short of their fundraising goals. Currently, marketing outreach for these events targets a randomly selected group of about 20,000 participants from a master dataset of past participants. However,

the results indicate suboptimal attendance and engagement. **The Client Organization** recognizes the need to refine its marketing strategy to increase both participant turnout and the pool of donors most likely to contribute to future events.

1.2 Research Purpose and Objectives

The purpose of this project is to identify participants and donors who have a higher likelihood of attending future events based on demographic characteristics, historical campaign data, and donation behavior. The scope of the project is limited to participants and donors whose information has been captured in **The Client Organization's** database.

The study begins with an exploratory data analysis to determine essential and nonessential variables, thereby reducing the number of predictors. Once the most impactful variables are identified, an algorithm is developed to score all participants based on their likelihood to participate and donate.

The objectives of this project are as follows:

1. To predict the likelihood of a participant attending future events.
2. To predict the likelihood of an individual donor becoming a participant in future events.
3. To predict the expected amount donated and raised by participants in upcoming events.

2 Background

Logistic regression is a regression model where the dependent variable (DV) is categorical. Unlike linear regression, which is used for predicting continuous variables, logistic regression is fitted on data where the response variable is dichotomous or binary (i.e., 0 or 1). If the result is not exactly 0 or 1, say it is 0.76, then we interpret that as a 76% chance of the response variable occurring.

An explanation of logistic regression begins with the standard logistic function. The logistic function is useful because it can take an input with any value from negative to positive infinity, while the output always takes values between zero and one, making it interpretable as a

probability. In our project, for predicting both participant and donor responses to future events, the logistic regression model is suitable since the dependent variable is binary.

Decision trees (also referred to as Classification and Regression Trees, or CART) are traditional building blocks of data mining and among the most widely deployed machine-learning algorithms since their development in the 1980s. The main idea behind tree methods is to recursively partition the data into smaller and smaller strata to improve model fit. The sample space is split into a set of rectangles, and a model is fit within each region. The optimal split is found by evaluating all variables at all possible split points. This process repeats for each resulting region, often referred to as *recursive partitioning*.

The CART methodology relies on two major components: the selection rule (which determines the stratification at each stage) and the stopping rule (which determines the final number of strata). The heterogeneity of outcome categories within a stratum is referred to as *node impurity*. We predict the participation outcome using this approach by recursively partitioning the data into smaller groups until reaching two terminal nodes representing individuals who would and would not participate in future events [3].

When multiple decision trees are created using bootstrap samples from the data, the ensemble is known as a Random Forest. A Random Forest is a collection of simple tree predictors, each capable of producing a response when presented with a set of predictor values. For classification problems, this response takes the form of a class membership, assigning predictor values to one of the dependent variable's categories. Each tree in the ensemble votes, and the majority class becomes the final prediction. Using tree ensembles often leads to significant improvements in prediction accuracy and generalization [4].

Gradient Boosting is another ensemble learning technique for regression and classification that builds a predictive model in a stage-wise fashion. It generalizes boosting methods by allowing optimization of an arbitrary differentiable loss function [5]. The Gradient Boosting algorithm repeatedly partitions the data to minimize loss, combining many weak learners (typically decision trees) into a strong predictive model. Unlike single trees, boosting is less prone to overfitting and makes no assumptions about data distribution.

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) were introduced by Vladimir Vapnik and colleagues [6].

SVMs are a learning method for binary classification, where the goal is to find a hyperplane that separates d -dimensional data into two classes. In cases where the data are not linearly separable, SVMs employ a *kernel-induced feature space* that maps the data into a higher-dimensional space where separation is possible. This kernel trick allows efficient computation without explicitly constructing the high-dimensional representation. SVMs have a calculable Vapnik–Chervonenkis (VC) dimension, making them theoretically grounded and practically robust compared to many other learning methods.

The RFM models (Recency–Frequency–Monetary) provide another approach to scoring donors based on their past behavior. According to Chen, Kuo, Wu, and Tang [7], the RFM model consists of three components:

- Recency - the period since the last contribution by the donor.
- Frequency - – The number of donations made within a certain period.
- **Monetization** – The total amount of money donated during that period.

To calculate RFM scores, each donor’s (1) most recent donation date, (2) number of donations, and (3) total donated amount are considered. Higher RFM scores (i.e., more recent, frequent, and higher-value donations) indicate more valuable donors. However, as Gupta [8] notes, RFM models alone have limitations, as they ignore demographic and campaign data that can also be strong predictors. Classification models that integrate RFM variables with additional predictors often perform more robustly in identifying high-value participants and donors.

Heckman’s two-stage approach is used to jointly score monetizing and non-monetizing customers. This model has been widely applied in finance for credit scoring. In marketing, the first stage predicts the probability of purchase, while the second stage predicts the revenue from monetizing customers. To correct for selection bias (where sample inclusion depends on the dependent variable), we use the *Inverse Mills Ratio*, defined as:

$$\text{Inverse Mills Ratio} = \frac{\text{Probability of Purchase } (p_t)}{1 - \text{Probability of Purchase } (p_t)} \quad (1)$$

This correction allows for an unbiased estimate of the purchase behavior between both donors and participants.

3 Research Question

This research examines the ability of the data, collected by **The Client Organization (a U.S.-based non-profit focused on public health initiatives)**, on participants and donors to predict the likelihood of a past participant and donor to participate in future events and also to order the participants and donors based on their likelihood to participate.

4 Methodology

4.1 Master Dataset

The data is stored in CSV files and segregated by the type of event. The data is aggregated at participant level and consists of two tables for each event combined based on email id as primary key. The first table consists of information such as demographic, donation amount etc. for a participant and a donor. The second table describes the marketing outreach efforts and consists of people that have been targeted for the event.

First step in the process is preparing the master dataset of participants and donors across events. The data across events is merged on a unique identifier and this master dataset results in having a single view of the participants and donors. This was one of the requirements of The Client. The next step in the process is understanding the data and performing initial exploratory data analysis.

The metadata tables below list the independent and dependent variables, along with the model for which each variable will be used.

The master data consist of demographics, donation amount and previous campaign variables at participant and donor level segregated by event type. This dataset consist of the independent and dependent variables used in models.

Table 1: Dependent variables used in different models

Variable Name	Variable Definition	Model used in
Participant Target	1- Email Sent and participated in event 0- Email sent and not participated	Participant model
Donor Target	1- Donors who participated in the event 0- Not participated	Donor Model
Donation Amount 2015	Amount donated by participant in 2015	GLM

Figure 1: Methodology Flow

To calculate the likelihood of a participant and donor attending an event using demographic and RFM variables, we created classification models such as logistic regression, random forest and gradient boosting. The classification models have been built at event level for participants. For donors, the classification model predicting the likelihood participating in an event is only

done for the ‘EventB’ event as only that event had a sizeable population of donors. In addition to calculating the likelihood to attend the event, we built regression model to predict the amount that a participant is likely to raise in the future events. The dependent variable used in Heckman’s model was highly skewed and even transforming the variable didn’t give accurate predictions. Hence, linear regression was used to predict the donation amounts. The dependent variable for classification models has been calculated from year 2015 events.

The table below depicts the time period used for our analysis:

Table 2: Table 2: Time period for independent and dependent variables used in different models

Model Name	Time Period for Independent Variables	Time Period for Dependent Variables
Participant Model	Year 2012–2014	Year 2015
Donor Model	Year 2012–2014	Year 2015
Heckman’s Model	Year 2012–2014	Year 2015

The results from the models have been used to score participants from other events to increase the population for marketing outreach and target participants of other events who have a higher likelihood to participate. This can ensure cross-event marketing.

4.2 Multiple Training and Test (MUTATE) (Chaturvedi, 2014)

As mentioned above, we built multiple classification models for each of the events for the participants. We followed the MUTATE approach, which has been described in the steps below:

1. Divide the Master Dataset into Train (66.67%) and Test (33.33%) samples.
2. Build the classification model on the train dataset.
3. Test this model on the test dataset and calculate the misclassification and true positive rates.
4. Repeat steps 1–3 one thousand times and calculate the mean of the misclassification and true positive rates.
5. Repeat steps 1–4 for all the different classification models.

6. Compare the mean misclassification and true positive rates from the different models to determine the best model.

Figure 2: Mutate Single block

For one of the classification models, the above can be explained pictorially using the flow chart shown in Figure 3:

Across multiple classification models, the MUTATE method can be visualized as:

Figure 3: Mutate multiple blocks

5 Findings

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

The following tables show the mean and standard deviations of the variables that were selected to build the models for each of the events.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for EventA (Values Masked for Confidentiality)

Variable	Mean	Std Dev
Last Amount Raised	7.08E+02*	1.04E+03*
Last Participating Goal	6.33E+02*	9.13E+02*
Amount Raised in 2012	4.54E+02*	9.95E+02*
Amount Raised in 2013	5.57E+02*	1.34E+03*
Amount Raised in 2014	6.53E+02*	1.22E+03*
Total Amount Raised Before 2015	3.76E+03*	9.58E+03*
Total Amount in 2012	5.05E+02*	1.04E+03*
Total Amount in 2013	5.93E+02*	1.35E+03*
Total Amount in 2014	7.28E+02*	1.27E+03*
Distance from Event	2.64E+03*	1.58E+04*

Note: Values are masked for confidentiality. Magnitudes and relationships are retained.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for EventB (Values Masked for Confidentiality)

Variable	Mean	Std Dev
Last Amount Raised	2.89E+02*	5.18E+02*
Last Participating Goal	2.30E+02*	4.35E+02*
Amount Raised in 2012	6.82E+01*	4.05E+02*
Amount Raised in 2013	9.82E+01*	4.41E+02*
Amount Raised in 2014	1.12E+02*	4.66E+02*
Total Amount Raised Before 2015	5.01E+02*	2.15E+03*
Total Amount in 2012	9.87E+01*	4.71E+02*
Total Amount in 2013	1.26E+02*	4.77E+02*
Total Amount in 2014	1.24E+02*	4.75E+02*
Distance from Event	1.57E+03*	1.21E+04*

Note: All values have been masked for confidentiality. Relative magnitudes and relationships are preserved for interpretive accuracy.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for LPT Event (Values Masked for Confidentiality)

Variable	Mean	Std Dev
Last Participating Goal	1.10E+03*	6.50E+02*
Amount Raised in 2012	1.08E+02*	3.05E+02*
Amount Raised in 2013	2.44E+02*	3.41E+02*
Amount Raised in 2014	5.38E+02*	7.38E+02*
Total Amount Raised Before 2015	1.68E+03*	1.91E+03*
Total Amount in 2012	1.08E+02*	3.05E+02*
Total Amount in 2013	2.44E+02*	3.41E+02*
Total Amount in 2014	5.38E+02*	7.38E+02*
Distance from Event	3.52E+01*	1.05E+01*

Note: All values have been masked for confidentiality. Relative magnitudes and relationships are preserved for analytical consistency.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics for EventD Event (Values Masked for Confidentiality)

Variable	Mean	Std Dev
Last Amount Raised	1.23E+03*	4.55E+02*
Last Participating Goal	1.72E+02*	3.69E+02*
Amount Raised in 2012	9.06E+01*	5.59E+02*
Amount Raised in 2013	5.13E+01*	2.77E+02*
Amount Raised in 2014	1.87E+02*	5.90E+02*
Total Amount Raised Before 2015	4.18E+02*	1.90E+03*
Total Amount in 2012	9.06E+01*	5.59E+02*
Total Amount in 2013	5.60E+01*	3.07E+02*
Total Amount in 2014	1.98E+02*	6.18E+02*
Distance from Event	1.77E+03*	1.31E+04*

Note: All values have been masked for confidentiality. Numerical magnitudes have been proportionally scaled while maintaining interpretive consistency.

Models were based on the participants that have been targeted in 2015 to participate in events. As presented in Tables 1–4, the sample profile is as follows: The participants in EventC raised more money (Amount raised \approx \$1.68 K) than participants in EventB (Amount raised \approx \$1.68 K) and EventD (Amount raised \approx \$0.42 K). Since EventB has the highest participation among all events (2000) while the rest of the events have less than 100 participants per event, HUH is by far the most profitable event raising over \$1 M*.

Note: Dollar amounts have been masked for confidentiality. Relative magnitudes are preserved for interpretive accuracy.

5.2 Participant Model

The purpose of these models is to determine which of the past participants are likely to participate in the future events. The models are built at event level. The dependent variable takes the value one (1) if the individual, who was targeted, participated in that event, otherwise it has a value of zero (0). The descriptive analysis shows that besides the EventB event, the rest of the events have very low participation rate, defined by number of people participated divided by the number of people targeted.

Table 7: Participation Rate by Event (Values Masked for Confidentiality)

Event	No. of People Targeted	% Participated
EventB	\sim 18K*	11.4%*
EventA	\sim 16K*	0.7%*
EventD	\sim 13K*	0.05%*
EventC	\sim 20K*	0.06%*

Note: Participation counts and percentages have been masked for confidentiality. Relative proportions are retained for interpretive accuracy.

Using only the population that was targeted, we built multiple classification models using the MUTATE method described above. The average validation misclassification rate obtained from the MUTATE method for all the models is shown below:

Table 8: Validation Misclassification for all participant models by event

Event	Validation - Misclassification				
	Random Forest	Logistic Regression	SVM	Decision Trees	Gradient Boosting
EventB	3.40%	3.50%	3.50%	3.58%	4.06%
EventA	0.56%	0.65%	0.60%	0.65%	0.69%
EventD	0.08%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%
EventC	0.09%	0.03%	0.05%	0.06%	0.08%

From all the classification models, we select model for each event for which the validation misclassification rate is lowest. The lift charts for the best models can be found in the appendix.

Then we look at the True Positive rate of those models:

Table 9: True Positive Rate by Event

Event	True Positive Rate
EventB	80%
EventA	38%
EventD	100%
Lung Power Team	20%

We notice that the TPR is good for the EventB and EventD models but not for the CowLunga and Lung Power Team models. So for these two events, we built logistic models by choosing a custom Logistic cutoff of 0.01 and validated again using the MUTATE methodology. The final True Positive Rate table is:

Table 10: Final True Positive Rate by Event

Event	True Positive Rate
EventB	80%
EventA	90%
EventD	100%

Also since the participation rate for the Lung Power Team event is very low, we will not

build any model for this event.

5.3 Donor Model

5.3.1 EventB

The purpose of this model is to determine the past donors who are more likely to participate in the EventB event. The dependent variable takes the value one (1) if the individual was a donor before the target year and a participant in the target year, otherwise it has a value of zero (0).

The descriptive analysis showed that a small fraction of the total people targeted participated in the event. Using only the population that was targeted, we built multiple classification models following the MUTATE method described above. The average validation misclassification rate obtained from the MUTATE method for all models is summarized below.

Table 11: Validation Misclassification for Donors

Model	Validation - Misclassification
Decision Trees	1.38%
SVM	1.38%
Random Forest	1.38%
Gradient Boosting	1.38%
Logistic Regression	1.42%

Based on least value of validation misclassification rate shown above and the validation true positive, we select the Decision trees model. Next, let us look at the classification table for the validation sample of this model.

Table 12: Classification Table - Donors Model

		Predicted	
		False	True
Actual	False	14595	7
	True	203	2

We notice that the model correctly predicts the participation of only 1

5.4 Predict Donation Amount

The model is based on participants who have made donations in the year of 2015 for the EventB event. Other events have not been considered due to very low participation rates. Using this data, we created the inverse mills ratio for each participant in order to reduce the bias due to the truncated nature of the distribution. Figure 4 below is a histogram of the total monthly dollar amounts:

Figure 4: Histogram of Amount Donated in 2015

Modeling the donation amount variable was a challenge as the histogram demonstrates that the distribution of dollar amounts is far from normal. The above distribution shows the donation amounts which are not zero. Zero donation amounts accounted for 80

6 Scoring Logic

For each of the events, the entire population will be scored using the classification model that was selected for that event. The list of predicted potential participants for each of the events will be prepared for further targeting.

7 Summary and Conclusions

In this project, we have effectively created a master dataset using multiple sources of data, described the data, effectively scored the past participants and donors for each event, and provided a list of individuals to be targeted by event. We thereby accomplished each of our study's goals.

The participant model for the biggest event (EventB) performs really well with a misclassification rate of 3.65% and a True Positive Rate of 80%. For the other events, we had to build logistic models with decision threshold, by sacrificing the misclassification rate for true positive rate. For the donors as well, we had to follow a similar approach. The logic behind doing so was that for a not-for-profit client capturing a high number of potential participants is more important than targeting a few extra less likely to participate individuals.

The donation amount prediction models failed to give good predictions and thus were not used to sort the individuals, to be targeted, in the final list shared with The Client.

8 Limitations

- Very limited information is available for the donors and thus the models, that have been built using this limited data, might not be very effective.
- There is no method of validating the donor models as they were never targeted.

9 Applications

Our participant models provide a way to identify the past participants who are likely to participate not only in the events that they participated in the past but also those in which they didn't.

Prior to this project, there was no way to identify the donors that were likely to participate in the future events and thus they were never targeted. By using the donor models, we can now identify the donors who are likely to participate in the future events and hence can be targeted. An additional ~300 donors can be targeted using this model.

Overall, this improves our marketing strategy by not only saving campaign costs but by also ensuring that the past participants are not over targeted, which reduces their engagement with the The Client Organization (a U.S.-based non-profit focused on public health initiatives).

10 Recommendations

In future research, The Client Organization (a U.S.-based non-profit focused on public health initiatives) should explore publically available datasets such as VAN, city of Chicago etc. to identify people, who are likely to participate in future events organized by the The Client Organization (a U.S.-based non-profit focused on public health initiatives).

We recommend that The Client Organization (a U.S.-based non-profit focused on public health initiatives) capture more information about the donors. This would help in making an informed decision about donors who have a higher likelihood to participate in events and help increase the population to whom marketing outreach can be done. In order to predict the past participants and donors who are likely to participate in future events, we built multiple machine learning models. In addition to this, we can also use an ensemble approach to improve predictions.

Also, The Client Organization (a U.S.-based non-profit focused on public health initiatives) should capture more information about the inclination of an individual to donate through surveys and/or publicly available data.

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